

Figure S2. Morphological parameters of male *Gryllus bimaculatus* crickets compared between all four experimental groups LD, LL₂, LL₅ and LL. Mean (\pm S.E.) of body length (n=12, 22, 22, and 41, respectively), wing length (n=12, 22, 22, and 41, respectively), tibia length (n=13, 20, 21, and 41, respectively), femur length (n=13, 20, 21, and 39, respectively), head width (n=12, 22, 22, and 41, respectively), pronotum length (n=12, 22, 22, and 39, respectively) and width (n=12, 22, 22, and 39, respectively), as well as body weight (n=11, 21, 22, and 36, respectively) are presented. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Inserted: Body condition index of the ratio of the crickets' individual weights divided by their individual lengths and compared between all four experimental groups LD, LL₂, LL₅ and LL (n=11, 22, 21, and 34, respectively), are presented. Single comparisons between treatments did not differ significantly (Kruskal Wallis with Dunn's post-hoc test, $p > 0.09$).